

CSWA Survey

The Committee on the Status of Women in Astronomy (CSWA) of the American Astronomical Society (AAS) was established in 1979. Its purpose is to "recommend to the Board of Trustees practical measures that the AAS can take to improve the status of women in astronomy and encourage their entry into this field." As we prepare to enter a new decade, the CSWA is interested in learning what specific areas and measures the astronomy community feels the committee should prioritize.

The following survey covers four topics that previous outreach has shown to be of interest to the community. Each section has a list of actions the committee could take to address an issue. Please rate each action according to how important or effective you feel it would be.

Each section also provides space for your suggestions.

To the extent that this survey might be interpreted as expressing any opinions, such opinions are those of the survey's authors alone and do not reflect the policy or position of the AAS.

Harassment and Bullying

Section Definitions:

Harassment – any form of aggressive pressure or intimidation. It is broader than sexual harassment. It can be based on the target's marginalized identity (e.g., gender, race, non-binary gender identification, disability, etc.).

Bullying – harassment from a position of superior power

Information Escrow – People submit a complaint, but no action is taken until one or more additional complaints are filed against the same person. This can help mitigate against reluctance to report potentially "minor" incidents, as well as keep a permanent record of complaints unaffected by institution transfers. This strategy is currently being discussed by the AAS Strategic Assembly.

Intersectional harassment -- harassment on the basis of more than one marginalized identity

1. Please evaluate the likely effectiveness of the following strategies that the AAS could pursue in order to prevent harassment.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not at all effective	A little effective	Somewhat effective	Very effective	No opinion
Enforce anti-harassment policies	<input type="radio"/>				
Create an information escrow	<input type="radio"/>				
Encourage departments and grad schools to include anti-harassment training both in their orientation activities and as part of their university policies	<input type="radio"/>				
Encourage bystander intervention training	<input type="radio"/>				
Encourage institutions to develop anti-harassment training that is customized to specific departments or locations	<input type="radio"/>				

**Hold
perpetrators
accountable
and provide
public,
anonymized
information
about
completed
investigations**

2. Other steps; please explain below

3. How should the AAS support those who may be or have been harmed by harassment and bullying?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not at all important	Somewhat important	Important	Very important	No opinion
Provide mentoring and/or counseling for those who have been adversely affected by harassment	<input type="radio"/>				
Teach people how to speak up and advocate for themselves in the case that they are harassed or bullied.	<input type="radio"/>				
Support people in deciding whether to file a complaint with the AAS.	<input type="radio"/>				
Support people in deciding whether to file a complaint with their home institution or other organizations.	<input type="radio"/>				

4. Other steps; please explain below

5. How should the CSWA and the AAS better coordinate with the AAS's other equity and inclusion committees (the Committee on the Status of Minorities in Astronomy [CSMA], the Committee for Sexual-Orientation & Gender Minorities in Astronomy [SGMA], and the Working Group on Accessibility and Disability [WGAD]) to address intersectional harassment?

6. Should the AAS encourage or implement training at colleges, universities and/or other locations? Why or why not? Do you have any suggestions about how the AAS should do this or what the content of the training should be?

7. If you have experience with anti-harassment training, what method(s) have you found to be effective and not effective?

8. Other comments on harassment and bullying?

Creating Inclusive Environments

9. Please evaluate the likely effectiveness of the following strategies that the AAS could pursue in fostering equity and inclusion across the board, especially for community members with intersectional marginalized identities.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not at all effective	A little effective	Somewhat effective	Very effective	No opinion
Educate members about ways to make diversity and inclusion a priority, not an afterthought	<input type="radio"/>				
Educate members on preventing reverse discrimination that may occur inadvertently in the pursuit of inclusivity	<input type="radio"/>				
Work with SGMA, WGAD, CSMA, CSWA, and others, to promote gender-neutral bathrooms, lactation rooms, and other provisions for marginalized groups	<input type="radio"/>				
Encourage universities to designate faculty members to support equity and inclusion	<input type="radio"/>				

issues not applicable to administrative offices such as Title VII / IX.

Encourage institutions to provide universal access to their facilities

Continue to provide support for regional meetings that focus on diversity, equity, and inclusion issues.

Continue to provide support for sessions that focus on diversity, equity, and inclusion issues at AAS meetings

Provide funding that increases the accessibility of networking and meeting spaces

Schedule conferences, seminars, and meetings at family-friendly times, be flexible when scheduling events, and provide video conferencing

capabilities

Increase equitable access to policy making and leadership roles within the AAS and its divisions; deliberately reach out to and involve individuals from across the entire astronomical community, especially underrepresented and under-resourced researchers and institutions, in policy and leadership roles.

10. Other steps; please explain below

11. Other comments on promoting equity and inclusion?

Professional Development, Hiring, and Retention

Section Definitions:

Two-body problem -- Both members of a couple needing jobs within commuting distance of each other.

12. Please evaluate the likely effectiveness of the following strategies that the AAS could pursue to improve professional development, hiring, and workplace environments.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not at all effective	A little effective	Somewhat effective	Very effective	No opinion
Offer a mentoring program for astronomers in all career stages	<input type="radio"/>				
Promote mentoring best practices	<input type="radio"/>				
Develop a salary database to support efforts toward equity in pay	<input type="radio"/>				
Support astronomers at all career stages from small institutions or non-academic organizations who may not have access to the same support network as those at larger institutions.	<input type="radio"/>				

Encourage institutions to implement ways to mitigate implicit bias in the workplace (including student settings)

Enable greater diversity (gender, ethnic, racial, geographical, institutional, etc.) in the pool of nominees for AAS and Division prizes and committees, and capture the data on the pools as a function of time.

Create a mentoring award

Facilitate leadership training (e.g., financial skills, high-level program management, personnel skills) for AAS members

Adopt best practices to encourage women and other members of marginalized groups to pursue leadership positions

Offer more resources such as workshops to combat imposter syndrome

For all career levels, provide funding and access to resources to mitigate the extra impact of caregiving on women

Encourage institutions to work to mitigate the two-body problem

Continue to encourage and provide opportunities for instructors, potential instructors, and teaching

assistants to learn new pedagogical and assessment techniques (i.e. workshops, mentoring for teaching)

Provide incentives and opportunities (such as awards, grants, and workshops) for instructors to develop and/or implement research-based inclusive teaching practices

Make dual-anonymous refereeing of papers mandatory

13. Other steps; please explain below

14. If you have experience with the two-body problem, please evaluate the effectiveness of the following approaches where applicable.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not at all effective	A little effective	Somewhat effective	Very effective	Not applicable
Be flexible - work from home	<input type="radio"/>				
Be flexible - accept work in separate locations temporarily	<input type="radio"/>				
Ask for compressed teaching schedules	<input type="radio"/>				
Negotiate a shared position	<input type="radio"/>				
Negotiate a second position	<input type="radio"/>				

15. Other steps; please explain below

16. Rate the importance of the following strategies that the AAS can adopt to help alleviate the two-body problem.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not at all important	Somewhat important	Important	Very important	No opinion
Encourage institutions to enable remote work	<input type="radio"/>				
Solicit personal accounts from members on their experiences with the two-body problem	<input type="radio"/>				
Find ways to encourage/mentor those in that situation	<input type="radio"/>				

17. Other steps; please explain below

18. Other comments on professional development, hiring, and retention?

Professional Ethics

19. Please evaluate the likely effectiveness of the following strategies that the AAS could pursue to improve professional ethics in the workplace.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not at all effective	A little effective	Somewhat effective	Very effective	No opinion
Survey early-career scientists about whether they have experienced academic dishonesty/ having their work stolen by more senior, scientists and, if so, how the experience has affected their careers	<input type="radio"/>				
Define harassment and/or other unethical behavior as a form of scientific misconduct and invoke a similar enforcement process as for scientific misconduct	<input type="radio"/>				
Withdraw AAS privileges,	<input type="radio"/>				

**such as
publishing in
its journals, in
response to
unethical
behavior**

**Remove AAS
honors, such
as prizes and
awards, in
response to
unethical
behavior**

**Enforce the
AAS Code of
Ethics
according to
the
provisions in
the code**

**Support
astronomers
in learning to
recognize
and
acknowledge
their
responsibility
to be 'good
citizens' in
areas where
their research
interacts with
societal
concerns**

**Provide an
award for
good service
to society
and/or good
citizenship in
the above
sense**

Support the AAS leadership in learning to be models for good citizenship in the above sense

Respond promptly when astronomers publicly engage in racism, sexism, heterosexism, cissexism, and/or ableism during meetings sponsored by the AAS and its divisions.

Develop a process for how/if to respond when astronomers publicly engage in racism, sexism, heterosexism, cissexism, and/or ableism during activities not specifically sponsored by the AAS and

its divisions.

20. Other steps; please explain below

21. Other comments on professional ethics?

Additional Feedback and Suggestions

22. Additional Feedback and Suggestions

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

